

THE IMPACT OF MIGRATION ON THE ELDERLY IN RURAL COMMUNITIES IN BEKWARRA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to investigate the impact of migration on the elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State Nigeria. Two research objectives were formulated for the study, from which questionnaire was constructed and used in data collection for this study. Duncan Theory of Migration was adopted for theoretical framework of the study. 184 study participants were engaged through distribution of questionnaires to randomly selected study respondents in randomly selected rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. The data collected were analysed descriptively through the use of statement tables. Findings of the study revealed that migration contribute to lack of care and lack of financial support to the elderly persons in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. The researchers recommended that the state government should work toward job creations in the rural areas to reduce youths' rural – urban migration, and government should provide social welfare services for the elderly as part of the State Civil Service Commission especially in the rural areas to create a supplementary care for the elderly.

Keywords: Elderly, youth, migration and Bekwarra

INTRODUCTION

The world is experiencing the largest movement of people in the 21st century since the creation of the earth. Most of these movements of the people have been caused by many factors which include war, terrorism, political crisis, economic recession, unemployment, and religious crisis. The world is moving and the young ones are on the move leaving the elderly left behind. According to World Migration Report (2020), human migration involves the movement of people from one place to another with intentions of settling, permanently or temporarily, at a new location (geographic region). This movement often occurs over long distances and from one country to another though internal migration (within a single country) is also possible and this is the dominant form of human migration in the world today (World Migration Report, 2020). Coxhead, Cuong & Vu (2015) posit that migration is often associated with better human capital at both individual and household level, and with better access to migration networks, facilitating a possible second move. Caves (2004) posits that age is also important for both work and non-work migration. People may migrate as individuals, in family units or in large groups (Coxhead, *et al.*, 2015).

The World's population is rapidly ageing with the relative increase in the older population most noticeable in the developing world (Hall, 2017). 12.3% of people in the world were aged 60 and above in 2015, and this percentage is expected to go up to 21.5% in 2050 (Macdonald, 2002). The number of countries with high-ageing and hyper-ageing populations is also on the rise; implying that the number of older people are increasing in the world (Hall, 2017). The UN has adopted 60 years and over as a cut-off age for “elderly” or “older person” to extend the eligibility criteria for ageing-related development projects (UN, 2001 in WHO, 2002). The UN definition for older person is generally not used across the globe. Therefore, national practices differ. The commonly used definition of “older person” is associated with the age at which one begins to receive pension benefits (WHO, 2002).

Africa's population is ageing much more quickly; by 2050, the number of people over 60 living in Africa will increase from just under 50 million to just under 200 million, and this unprecedented demographic shift is having profound implications for society, influencing people's social, economic and political lives (Hall, 2017). Hall further maintained that Africa is characterised by complex population movements, including refugees, asylum-seekers, economic migrants, victims of trafficking, smuggled migrants, unaccompanied minors and other migrants, as well as rural-urban migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs). To better capture the experiences of older people in situations of migration in Africa, it is fundamental to acknowledge that local context, legal status and gender have significant impacts on the agency and the migration experiences of older people (Hall, 2017). Peters and Bassey (2019) posited that the elderly experiences are captured in the rural areas. Wilson *et al.*, (2023) are of the position that in Africa, the experiences of the elderly are correlated with what they consider good health.

Migration is related to age and its impacts are related to age. The movement of the young has directed impacts on the older or aged population. Though migration has many positive and negative impacts, the elderly has always been at the receiving side of the effects of migration. Migration in Nigeria has witnessed the movement of the young from the rural areas to the urban centres leaving the elderly behind. The rate of migration in the southern part of Nigeria is one of the highest in the country and is fuelled by population growth and the adverse economic and political situation in the country (Olajide, 2014). Olajide (2014)

further maintained that migration in this part of the nation has led to a continued removal of potential human resources from the rural areas to the urban areas across the nation. In the southeast of Nigeria, only about 22% of the people are rural residents. Nwajiuba (2011) posits that there is a very high degree of rural-urban migration with 78% of indigenes residing outside their homes. About 32% reside within the southeast region but not in their home communities and 14% reside in locations within Nigeria but outside the south east. Hall (2017) opined that population aging and migration pose a potential crisis of old-age support in less-developed countries (LDCs) like Nigeria particularly in rural areas that lack institutional support mechanisms for the aged.

In Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State of Nigeria, the extent of migration of the young people especially from the Bekwarra community is on the high due to socio-economic conditions for survival within the area. The struggle for survival has exerted only one thing on the young population of the Bekwarra people of Bekwarra Local Government Area and that is “migration”. Though the movement of the young people is mainly for greener pasture at urban centres, most of the elderly are the parents of these young people and most of them desire, encourage, support, and pray for the movement of their children from the rural area to the urban centres in order to find some jobs or other means of livelihood so that in turn, there might be remittance for the up keep and welfare of the elderly parents. What we have today is that most of these elderly persons are still hoping for the fulfilment of their expectations of the emigrant children, and are still watching the road for the return or visit of their emigrant children. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the challenges faced by elderly persons as a result of the migration of their children or wards in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria are within the class of citizens that are classified into the aged, and old age is characterized with fading in body composition, loss of strengths, loss of sight, and different kinds of diseases which make the need for availability and provision of care and supports services to be on high demands. Health crises like stroke, rheumatism, pains, partial and complete blindness, diabetes, hypertension, and paralysis which contribute to both physical and psychological health challenges, have been known issues with elderly in Cross River State which positioned the elderly in the place of care and support. Majority of the elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State are living in abject poverty as they depend on their children and relatives who migrated from rural communities to other urban places in search for better life. It can be said that most of the elderly are living as the abandoned, the rejected and the lonely. This is because those children and relatives who supposed to offer care, support and financial assistance are living far from Bekwarra making it in most time difficult for these elderly to access their children, relatives, and their supports. Since majority of the elders in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State are poor, the need for care and support seems to be a serious challenge as most of their children and relatives have been taken away from their reach as a result of migration from Bekwarra to other parts of the Cross River State, Nigeria, and the world. If something is not done to transform Bekwarra rural communities and other

rural areas through human-driven development to reduce youth migration, the aged population will continue to suffer and diminish or suffer extermination due to migration in the coming years.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The major objective of the study was to examine the impact of migration on the elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. examine how lack of care affects the elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State, as a result of migration.
- ii. investigate how lack of financial support affects the elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State, as a result of migration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Migration

Migration is the movement of either people or animals from one area to another (Vocabulary.com, 2021). According to McDonald (2002), Depending on the goal and reason for relocation, people who migrate can be divided into three categories: migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers. Each category is defined broadly as the mixed circumstances might occur and motivate a person to change their location. As such, migrants are traditionally described as persons who change the country of their residence for general reasons and purposes. These purposes may include the search for better job opportunities or healthcare needs. This term is the most generally defined one as anyone changing their geographic location permanently can be considered migrants. Refugees are not narrowly defined and are described as persons who do not relocate willingly (McDonald, 2002). The reasons for the refugees' migration usually involve war actions within the country or other forms of oppression, coming either from the government or non-governmental sources. Refugees are usually associated with people who must unwillingly relocate as fast as possible; hence, such migrants will likely relocate undocumented (McDonald, 2002).

Thewordpoint.com (2020) maintained that asylum seekers are associated with persons who also leave their country unwillingly, yet, who also do not do so under oppressing circumstances such as war or death threats. The motivation to leave the country for asylum seekers might involve an unstable economic or political situation in the country or high rates of crime. Thus, asylum seekers relocate predominantly in order to escape the degradation of the quality of their lives (Thewordpoint.com, 2020). Nomadic movements are normally not regarded as migrations, as the movement is generally seasonal, there is no intention to settle in the new place, and only a few people have retained this form of lifestyle in modern times. Temporary movement for travel, tourism, pilgrimages, or commuting is also not regarded as migration in the absence of an intention to live and settle in the visited places (McDonald, 2002).

Impacts of Migration

Migration is becoming a very important subject for the life of cities. Many opportunities and attraction of big cities pull large numbers of people to big cities. Migration

can have positive as well as negative effects on the life of the migrants (toppr.com, 2021).

Positive Impact

Unemployment

- is reduced and people get better job opportunities.
- Migration helps in improving the quality of life of people.
- It helps to improve social life of people as they learn about new culture, customs, and languages which helps to improve brotherhood among people.
- Migration of skilled workers leads to a greater economic growth of the region.
- Children get better opportunities for higher education.
- The population density is reduced and the birth rate decreases.

Negative Impact

- The loss of a person from rural areas, impact on the level of output and development of rural areas.
- The influx of workers in urban areas increases competition for the job, houses, school facilities etc.
- Having large population puts too much pressure on natural resources, amenities and services.
- It is difficult for a villager to survive in urban areas because in urban areas there is no natural environment and pure air. They have to pay for each and everything.
- Migration changes the population of a place, therefore, the distribution of the population is uneven in India.
- Many migrants are completely illiterate and uneducated, therefore, they are not only unfit for most jobs, but also lack basic knowledge and life skills.
- Poverty makes them unable to live a normal and healthy life.
- Children growing up in poverty have no access to proper nutrition, education or health.
- Migration increased the slum areas in cities which increase many problems such as unhygienic conditions, crime, pollution etc.
- Sometimes migrants are exploited.
- Migration is one of the main causes of increasing nuclear family where children grow up without a wider family circle. (toppr.com, 2021)

Effects of Migration on the Elderly

According to Kuhn, Everett, & Silvery (2011), population aging and migration pose a potential crisis of old-age support in less-developed countries (LDCs), particularly in rural areas that lack institutional support mechanisms, such as nursing homes. Kuhn *et al.*, (2011) further posit that in recent studies of the impact of children's migration on elders left behind by migrant kin suggest an alternative conclusion. Rather than creating a healthcare vacuum in rural areas, migration can actually be a valuable resource for improving health and development (Ozden & Schiff, 2007). An emerging literature has begun to address such effects, generally finding better health among elders with migrant children than among those without (Kuhn 2005). This literature, however, has yet to address issues of self-selection bias, whereby individuals who are most likely to remain in good health are also most likely to have

migrant children, making it difficult to establish whether children's migration actually causes better health (Kuhn *et al.* 2011). According to Ononkpono, Peters, & Usoro (2020), these elderly have challenges accessing health care for good health.

In addressing these concerns, Kuhn *et al.* (2011) modelled the effects of internal migration of prime-age adults on the health of parents left behind in rural areas of Indonesia. Kuhn *et al.* (2011) further maintained that in Indonesia, as in many less-developed countries (LDCs), absolute numbers and relative proportions of elderly among the total population are rising as fertility and mortality rates decline, placing an increasing health burden on family members and health care systems. According to Brown (2003), internal migration opportunities in Indonesia have been facilitated by a steady rise in both gross domestic product (GDP) and foreign investment in conjunction with increased labour force human capital.

Researchers like Kuhn *et al.* (2011); DaVanzo & Chan (1994); and Hermalin (2002) after controlling for age and sex variations, researchers have found intergenerational social support networks to be the most important predictors of old-age health and survival in LDCs, even in the face of declining family size. By contrast, studies in LDCs offer limited support for the direct impact of socioeconomic status, wealth, or education on health that are found in many wealthy nations (Kuhn *et al.* 2011). This shows that increasing levels of migration from rural areas have generated concerns regarding the social penalty for left-behind elders in the form of reduced functional support and increased psychosocial isolation (Chang 2002; Rahman 2009).

Other researchers have suggested that parents may actually benefit from their child's migration (Beard & Kunharibowo 2001; Frankenberg *et al.* 2002; Keasberry 2001; Knodel and Debavalya 1997; Kuhn 2005, 2006; Rahman 2000; Toyota *et al.* 2007). Kuhn (2005) in evaluating the effects of migration on the health of left-behind elders in rural Bangladesh, found out that compared with elders with no migrant children, those with children living outside their district or country were both 30% more likely to be in good health (according to self-reported health and physical exams) and 30% less likely to have died in a subsequent four-year follow-up period. Therefore, rather than being a catalyst for destroying traditional systems of health production through children's absence, migration may instead play a key role in migrant children's old-age support. Such findings support the well-established expectations of the "New Economics of Labour Migration," a cooperative model in which migrants share risks and resources with the left-behind and base their migration decisions on pre-existing household conditions and parental needs (Kreager 2006; Kuhn 2003; VanWey 2004). The Elderly are abandoned especially in the rural areas in Nigeria (Ottong & Peters, 2025).

Cooperative models according to Kuhn *et al.* (2011), point to clear pathways that may offset any social penalty associated with children's migration. Remittances or economic transfers from migrants to the left-behind can improve the standard of living of the elderly daily (Asis 2006; Frankenberg & Kuhn 2004). Kuhn *et al.* (2011) further maintained that migrant children may provide significantly larger financial transfers during a health crisis, acting as a basic health insurance policy. According to Frank & Hummer (2002), increasing levels of technology can facilitate communication concerning health-related information via phone calls or the Internet. Improved communication may also mitigate the social penalties associated with having a migrant child (Knodel & Saengtienchai 2007; Kreager 2006).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Duncan Theory of Migration

According to Sociologydiscussion.com (2022), O. D. Duncan, in his book, “The Theory and Consequences of Mobility of Farm Population”, has presented a theory regarding the mobility of population engaged in agriculture. His theory is the combination of microscopic and macroscopic active forces in the process of migration. According to Duncan, whatever effects are created by changes in structural factors of the country, the same effects are caused by migration. Thus, for achieving many structural aims, migration is the functional alternative to social change.

Generally, the following factors are responsible for migration:

1. Economic and Technical Causes:

They relate to the changes occurring in the technique of production, in methods and structure of agricultural operations, in market structure, in price situation, in specialisation, in production, and in relative changes in the wage level, etc.

2. Social Causes:

The social causes are the development of institutional structure, policies regarding public land and production, development of transport and communication systems, population growth, increase in knowledge and its expansion, class-conflicts and competition, disarrangement coming in social degradation and structure of administration, changing needs of maintenance of family, etc.

3. Personal Causes:

In personal causes are included unsatisfied needs, increase in the intelligence of persons and expanding horizon of knowledge, health, emotions of alienation, views regarding neighbours, imagination power, nature, emotions, etc.

4. Natural Causes:

The natural causes pertain to environment and atmosphere, frequent existence of diseases, floods, earthquake, droughts, malaria, hookworm, seasonal changes, land erosion, etc.

5. Other Causes:

There are some miscellaneous causes which affect migration. They are labour problems, strikes, riots, increase in real wealth, search of new means or ending up of the supply of old resources, etc. (Sociologydiscussion.com, 2022)

Whatever the cause of migration may be, the effects of migration on the origin have always been felt mostly by the elderly as migration in its first stage has always been engaged by the youths. Elderly or aged migration is always a case of follow-up migration when and if the migrated child or children can settle and are capable of accommodating the aged parent that was left behind. Those elders who have no such opportunity of attaining such migration, in most cases, are always affected by a series of challenges as a result of losing the younger generation who are supposed to replace their ageing strength with their youthful strength in labour and services to their parents and community. This has been the case of the study area, in the Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts descriptive research design because the study is intended to acquire information on the effects of migration on the elderly in Bekwarra Local Government Area.

The researchers made the study in such a way that various quantitative primary data collection techniques were employed. This was to make it convenient to examine the effects of migration on the elderly in Bekwarra Local Government Area.

The study was conducted in the Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. Bekwarra Local Government Area is in the Northern Senatorial District of Cross River State. There are ten political wards in the local government and these are; Abuochiche, Afrike Ochagbe, Afrike Okpeche, Benten, Gakem, Ibiragichi, Nyanya, Otukpuru, Ugboro and Ukpah. Bekwarra Local Government Area has its headquarters at Abuochiche. It is bounded in the north by Benue State, South by Ogoja Local Government Area, East by Obudu Local Government Area and West by Yala Local Government Area. The major population groups of the local government area are Ujia, Unwapu, Unwagba Oli West, Oti East, Eya Aba, Beten, Uduo, Eya Adie, Ika-Ichia, Udomu, Atibulum, Afrike-Okpeche, Okpeche, Ikachor, Ugboro, Ukpah, Anyikang, Abuochiche, and Ochagbe. The major economic activities in the area include agriculture, cattle/goat and poultry rearing and trading. The majority of the indigenes are farmers whose produce are sold within and outside the state. The area has very rich cultural heritage. The major traditional festival is the New Yam Festival held during the first week of September yearly. The traditional market days are; Udama, Ugbada, Uchagu, Ugidi and Achanya.

From the calculated sample size out of Bekwarra population, the researchers decided to use 184 as the sample size (n) of the study. Despite the calculated sample size, the researcher was only able to engage 184 study participants for the study. Data were collected through the use of a questionnaire. The questionnaires were structured with close-ended questions which made it easy for the respondents to provide unbiased answers in an objective manner. The questions were on issues that sought to collect information on the effects of migration on the elderly in Bekwarra village in Bekwarra local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. Data collected by the researchers were analysed descriptively through the use of statistical analysis involving tables of frequency distributions with the help of Microsoft Office 2010 statistical analysis.

FINDINGS

Lack of Care on the Elderly and Migration

Table 1: Lack of care affects the elderly in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State as a result of migration of the youth

Statements	Yes	No
Children leave their poor parents behind when migrating	169	19
Most children do not have people set up to replace them in term of services provision or care giving to their parents	123	61
Most children who migrate do not have the financial power to make provision of care giver for their parents	94	90
Most of the parents left behind cannot take care of themselves in many situations	78	106
Money sent as remittance to some poor and illiterate parents through relatives for care giving do not reach them as it supposed to	91	93

Source: Researchers' Field work, (2025)

The analysis of Table 1 shows that on the opinion that children leave their poor parents behind when migrating, 169 were of “Yes” while 19 were of the opinions “No”. On the opinion that most children do not have people set up to replace them in term of services provision or care giving to their parents, 123 were of yes and 61 were of no. On the opinion that most children who migrate do not have the financial power to make provision of care giver for their parents, 94 were of yes and 90 were of the no. On the opinion that most of the parents left behind cannot take care of themselves in many situations study respondents on the opinion that children leave their poor parents 78 respondents were of the yes while 106 respondents were of the no. On the last opinion which states that money sent as remittance to some poor and illiterate parents through relatives for care giving do not reach them as it supposed, 91 respondents were of the yes while 93 were of the no opinion. The analysis of Table 4.6 shows that the majority of the study respondents were of the yes opinions.

Lack of Financial Support and Migration

Table 2: Lack of financial support affects the elderly in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State as a result of migration

Statements	Yes	No
Children support their parents financially and when leaving, their parents lack such supports	87	97
Most children do not have enough to send back home for their parents' wellbeing	103	81
Poor parents are living in unfilled hope of having help from migrated children	98	86
Some relatives have refuse to assist such parents because of belief in remittance which they are expected to enjoy	79	105
Money sent as remittance to some poor and illiterate parents through relatives do not reach them as it supposed to	107	77

Source: Researchers' Field Work (2025)

The analysis of Table 2 shows that on the opinion that children support their parents financially and when leaving their parents lack such supports, 87 were of “Yes” while 97 were of the opinions “No”. On the opinion that most children do not have enough to send back home for their parents' wellbeing, 108 were of yes and 81 were of no. On the opinion that poor parents are living in unfilled hope of having help from migrated children, 98 were of yes and 86 were of the no. On the opinion that some relatives have refuse to assist such parents because of belief in remittance which they are expected to enjoy, 79 respondents were of the yes while 105 respondents were of the no. On the last opinion which states that money sent as remittance to some poor and illiterate parents through relatives do not reach them as it is supposed to, 107 respondents were of the yes while 77 were of the no opinion.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study sought to examine the impact of migration on the elderly in Bekwarra community in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State Nigeria. After using the statement tables, the researchers observed that from the analysis of responses of study respondents; there is great impact of lack of care on the elderly in some rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State, as a result of migration. This implies that most of the elderly are faced with lack of care by their children due to migration. These findings gives credence to Kuhn *et al.* (2011) who posits that migration pose a potential crisis of old-age support in less-developed countries (LDCs), particularly in rural areas that lack institutional support mechanisms, such as nursing homes. For objective two, the analysis of the statement table shows that; there is great influence of lack of financial support affects the elderly in Bekwarra in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State, as a result of migration. This emerged from the responses of the study respondents who accepted the

statements in favour of the result. These findings agree with Kuhn *et al.* (2011) who modelled the effects of internal migration of prime-age adults on the health of parents left behind in rural areas of Indonesia. The implication of the findings is that the migration of the young people of rural communities is greatly affecting the life and survival of the elderly in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

In this study, data were collected and analysed descriptively through the use of statement tables. The study which sought to investigate the impact of migration on the elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State Nigeria, revealed that migration contributes to lack of care, and lack of financial support of the elderly in rural communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The implication of these findings is that youth's migration from the rural communities has great effects on the elderly persons especially in the rural areas of Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher derived the following recommendations;

1. The state government should work toward job creations in the rural areas to reduce rural – urban migration.
2. Government should provide social welfare services as part of the State Civil Service Commission for the elderly especially in the rural areas in order to create a supplementary care for the elderly.
3. Children who leave their aged parents as a result of migration should remember to make good plan for their wellbeing.

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